

REVEALING PARADIGM SHIFTS AND LINCHPIN FACETS IN SHAPING INDIA'S PUBLIC HOUSING POLICIES: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Public policies, especially housing policies, provide hope for disadvantaged segments of society to meet basic necessities. Since India's independence, public welfare housing schemes have been designed and executed with the aim of alleviating housing deprivation. Since then, the Indian government has made a number of initiatives in this field, but with differing paradigms of approach and execution frameworks. The premise remained the same, i.e. providing mass housing to the destitute, but the target beneficiaries, goal defined, approach taken, and result achieved have evolved. Important housing policies have been analysed from India's independence to the latest in order to analyse the paradigm shift and significant components. In the review, they are categorised according to their paradigm, followed by a discussion on the same and identification of overall significant aspects. The approach adopted has yielded lessons from which new policies have been established in an effort to improve and more effectively accomplish the goals. These key elements are adequate to determine the validity of any policy implementation. These factors may be used to evaluate any present housing policy or as a guide for future housing policies. The policy execution system must be robust enough to maintain optimism for scheme goals.

Keywords: Public Housing; Housing for All; Affordable Housing; Slum Redevelopment; Housing Finance

INTRODUCTION

Housing is an important problem in in of itself, especially for developing nations with acute housing shortages and deficiency. Housing-related shortcomings in a country are remedied via public housing initiatives in which the government satisfies the need for mass housing for disadvantaged parts of society. After attaining independence, the Indian government enacted a variety of efforts to address housing-related issues, some of which were goals-based or comprehensive policies. Each time, the goal was to eliminate housing deprivation, but the approach evolved in response to shifting demands and lessons acquired from previous housing programmes. This evolution culminated in a paradigm shift in the execution of housing policy. The traces of change must be evaluated within the framework of the technique employed for the development of the plans. It is now essential to analyse this transition, which drove policymakers to restructure the strategy for policy objectives, purpose, beneficiaries, and stakeholders in order to obtain greater success from the results.

METHODOLOGY

Since India's independence, all major schemes, plans, programmes, policies, and initiatives have been comprehensively reviewed and categorised based on similar outcomes and policy framework approaches in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the housing policy approaches adopted by India's policymakers and the critical implementation aspects. Several research papers, studies, booklets on housing policies published by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs of the Government of India, and policy-related articles from secondary sources have been reviewed.

The review of public housing schemes in India

Changing paradigms have necessitated a review and differentiation of housing regulations. In addition, the classifications include the most significant post-implementation consequences and primary outcomes. Following a timeline, the organisation begins with India's independence and concludes with the current housing policy where the housing policy trajectory has been divided into six periods, presumably representing major shifts in housing policy regimes.

Housing as a social benefit (1947-1965)

State-led loan-based programmes, such as the Subsidized Housing Scheme for Industrial Workers & EWS (1952) and the Low Income Housing Scheme (1954), were established immediately after independence to provide stable housing for the nation's labour force. Several slums were renovated as part of the Slum Clearance & Improvement Scheme in exchange for moderate rates (1956). In addition, programmes such as Rental Accommodation for State Government Personnel (1959) existed to offer government employees (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2016) with rental housing. On a ten-year loan basis, land development programmes such as the Land Acquisition and Development Scheme (1959) were permitted to acquire land for public housing (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020). The Rent Control Act of 1961 was also enacted to safeguard these tenants from eviction (IIHS, 2011). During this time period, the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (1952), the National Building Organisation (1954), and a number of housing boards were established to facilitate the implementation of public housing plans (M. Mukherjee et al., 2016). These initiatives were part of the Specific Housing Program for Particular Groups, which encouraged housing as a form of economic growth (Khan & Sharma, n.d.). However, various challenges, including a lack of funds, illegal private home growth, and an inefficient and unjustified housing site, prompted a paradigm shift (WRI INDIA, 2019).

Economic Contribution of Housing (1965-1985)

In order to alleviate the burden of providing public housing to the needy, the government has segmented its approach to the housing deficit by allowing economically privileged classes such as MIGs and HIGs to build their own dwellings (Khaire & Jha, 2022). During this time, following the third five-year plan, the state government also provided funds for public housing constructions (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2002) (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020). Prior to that period, central governments operated as suppliers rather than facilitators (Mukherjee et al., 2016). This has been achieved by establishing home finance

organisations such as HUDCO (1970) and HDFC (1977) from which the middle class can acquire a mortgage loan (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2016). This has led to housing construction being recognised as an economic contributor (IIHS, 2011). Under a public-private partnership, the remaining funds were allocated to slum rehabilitation projects, including Environment Improvement of Urban Slums (1972) and Sites and Services Schemes (1980), as well as the creation of vital urban infrastructure. Schemes of urban low cost sanitation for freedom of scavengers (1981) for degrading practise of hauling night soil by converting pit latrines to flush latrines led to the eradication of society's most significant taboo (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2022a) (Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation, 2011) (M. Mukherjee et al., 2016). This time was marked by the establishment of housing, followed by its rapid reorganisation and the government structure, resulting in implementation delays and limited community engagement (Nallathiga, 2007) (Sinha & Nishad 2021) (WRI INDIA, 2019). All of these factors contributed to an increase in the private housing stock (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2002).

Housing as a Fundamental Human Need (1985-1992)

Subsequently, housing was regarded as a matter of greater importance and a prerequisite for healthy, compassionate living (Chhaya, 2021) (UNITED NATIONS, 2021). Urban Basic Service Scheme (1986); Indira Awas Yojna (1985), a more comprehensive effort like National Housing Policy (1990) to ensure employment generation in construction industry through forward and backward linkages; provided loans and subsidies for the construction of night shelters and sanitation facilities for pavement dwellers with the assistance (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2016) (Ministry of Rural Development, 2020) (IIHS, 2011). Efforts and attention were redirected to underserved portions of public housing by enabling the construction of self-build dwellings for economically stable families (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020) (M. Mukherjee et al., 2016). However, due to the simultaneous introduction of different housing plans, policy objectives converged, and as a result, interventions remained scattered and aims remained jumbled (WRI INDIA, 2019).

Housing as Product (1992-2005)

As a result of global liberalisation and privatisation, there was a major paradigm change after 1992. In addition, the 73rd and 74th amendments to the Indian Constitution gave urban local governments administrative, financial, and implementation duties, empowering them to oversee the execution of housing initiatives within their jurisdictions (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2022a) (Khaire & Jha, 2022). The three levels of government became the key stakeholders, with the federal government serving merely as a facilitator and not as a direct provider (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2016) (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020). The housing market shifted from a necessity to a marketable commodity as a result of the growth in privatisations brought on by globalisation (Khaire & Jha, 2022). The 1996 National Slum Development Program addressed slums as a separate entity. 2 million Housing Program (1998) and Valmiki Ambedkar Awas Yojana (2001) encouraged the construction of dwellings through the use of government loans (IIHS, 2011). Financial institutions strengthened their foundations, thereby establishing a legal home credit market (IIHS, 2011) (Housing for All' Mission Directorate Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs Government of India, 2022). As local governments were unable

to demonstrate their capacity for implementing effective mass housing schemes, a segment of society's poor remained disadvantaged (M. Mukherjee et al., 2016). In reality, these local governments had no other funding options (Paul, 2016). As a result, the limited community engagement, ineffective implementation techniques, construction delays, and housing quality remained poor (Sinha & Nishad, 2021) (WRI INDIA, 2019) (RBI Bulletin, 2018). Privatization promoted expansion in private housing, but the financing choices for low-income populations remained unknown (Sivam & Karuppanan, 2002) (Gopalan & Venkataraman, 2015).

Housing to be 'Affordable' (2005-2015)

Since the turn of the 21st century, rising costs for land, building materials, and labour have steadily brought the issue of affordability to the forefront (Karmali & Weng, 2022). The housing issue was thereafter viewed as an element of regional, metropolitan, and rural urban planning. Consequently, JnNURM established public housing as a comprehensive, reform-driven, planned urban development (2005). Multiplication of local governments that made the implementation process more complex, where it was difficult to maintain inter-departmental coordination, thus delaying the process of approvals and sanctioning, which consequently increased construction costs (Sinha & Nishad, 2021) (Mukherjee et al., 2016) (Nallathiga, 2007) (IIHS, 2011). In addition, local administrations lacked the expertise to successfully implement the entire operation (Paul, 2016) (WRI INDIA, 2019). Numerous constraints associated with financing mechanisms, such as the lack of acceptable alternative funding sources and credit lending channels for low-income groups such as LIGs and EWSs, lead to the ineffectiveness of the financing mechanisms on the beneficiaries (Tiwari & Rao, 2011) (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2022a) (IIHS, 2011). The Size Fits All implementation strategies that favoured new buildings over in-situ restoration resulted in inappropriate and unjustified public housing for recipients (Gopalan & Venkataraman, 2015) (Sengupta et al., 2022) (Pophaliya & Mata, 2019). Public-private collaborations to make housing more affordable are supported by the National Urban Housing & Habitat Policy (2007) and the Rajiv Awas Yojna (2011) (Kumar, 2009). From Rajiv Awas Yojna onwards, a two-pronged, paradigm-shifting method was utilised, with one component for the rebuilding of slums and the other for affordable housing in partnership (AHP).

Housing for All (2015-2022)

Following the adjustment of the Rajiv Awas Yojna in 2015, the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojna was initiated with revised housing shortage targets in accordance with the TG-12 Report (Tiwari & Rao, 2011). This was done in order to meet the needs of the country's growing population (Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs Government of India, 2022a). This all-encompassing housing initiative is intended for both urban and rural areas, and it employs a diverse approach that falls under four PMAY verticals (Sinha & Nishad, 2021) (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2021). Given that the provision of housing is under the purview of individual states, the purpose of this programme is to make it possible for public housing provision to be adapted flexibly to meet the requirements of individual states (CRISIL, 2018) (Mukherjee et al., 2016) (KPMG, 2014). The technique may be altered to fit the requirements of individual states, and those states were given permission

to design their own implementation frameworks (Kamath, 2020) (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2021) (WRI INDIA, 2019). As a consequence of this, a great number of states have adopted PMAY verticals or other strategies (Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs Government of India, 2022c) (Kamath, 2020). By the year 2022, it is anticipated that the housing shortage would have been completely resolved (Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs Government of India, 2022b) (Thornton Bharat, 2021). In addition to that, this policy gathers together progressive approaches to housing, such as the Light House Projects (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2022a) (Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2022b) (Centre for Science and Environment, 2020). It was decided to continue the plan through December 31, 2024, with only three verticals: beneficiary-led building, in-situ slum remediation, and affordable housing in partnership (Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs Government of India, 2019) (Goel Dr, 2018). Due to the fact that the goals of the vertical were finally accomplished, the component credit link subsidy programme was eradicated (Rumi Aijaz, 2022).

DISCUSSION

Paradigm shift identification

According to the most reliable sources, the concept and knowledge of the housing problem that was held by various governments at various times was mirrored in some manner by the housing laws that were enacted during those times (Bharti Madhu & Divi Sriram, 2019) (Congressional Research Service, 2014). On the other hand, as the significance and gravity of this subject matter grew, so did the breadth of the research into it, which brought to light the complexities of the circumstance. Beginning not long after the country gained its independence, the concept was limited to housing developments for specific groups, such as employees employed by the government, industrial workers, and so on (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020) (M. Mukherjee et al., 2016) (Khaire & Jha, 2022). Then, it was realised that housing might help to contribute to economic development and the removal of the need for manual scavenging (Khaire & Jha, 2022). Through this programme, an effort was made to better the health of those who work in the sanitation industry. The housing market became significantly more controlled as a result of the establishment of a great number of institutions, including financial establishments such as HUDCO and HDFC (Khaire & Jha, 2022).

After that, the paradigm shifted from a fragmented approach to an integrated strategy in the Indira Awas Yojana, which was intended for rural areas in which housing was regarded as a fundamental needed human need regardless of location, in contrast to earlier schemes, which were primarily urban (Paul, 2016) (A. Mukherjee et al., 2020). This strategy was intended for rural areas in which housing was regarded as a basic needed human need regardless of location (Reddy & Ramesh, 2018). At the stage of implementation, however, many schemes, each of which was dependent on the goals, continued to produce chaos (Bharti Madhu & Divi Sriram, 2019) (Deloitte, 2016). The proliferation of privately owned and self-built homes continued in the backdrop (Paul, 2016). Then, globalisation promoted housing to become a separate commodity that could be sold via improving market lending, public-private partnerships, and the empowerment

of local governments (Sengupta et al., 2022). This was done so that housing could be bought and sold (Brahmbhatt, 2020). The relevance of comprehensive integrated planning in the 21st century was then realised, and JnNURM was presented as reform-driven urban planning rather than simply housing. The method was first enlarged to include two prongs in the Rajiv Awas Yojna, and then it was expanded to include numerous prongs in the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojna (Khan Dr. Nisar, 2019) (KPMG, 2014).

Unrevealing linchpin facets in policy implementation

Certain fundamental aspects of policy implementation, in particular housing plans and policies, have the potential to either act as restrictions or as assistance in the process of policy implementation. While analysing the critical nodes of policy execution in a variety of housing policies implemented in India since the country's independence, the common nodes have stayed consistent. In the process of carrying out PMAY, other concerns have also been addressed and resolved. Capital to implement, location of public dwellings, Financial affordability, Beneficiary participation, Identification of beneficiaries, advantages to EWS or LIG, departmental coordination, quality standards of public housing delivered, land assembly for housing, stock public dwellings, the capabilities of executing agencies, Timeframe for Construction and Approval, Multiplicity of government bodies, Housing financing accessibility, Governmental faith, entire implementation procedure outlined, employing technology, Monitoring mechanisms, Planning norms, participation of private entities and Joint ventures, etc. can be summed up as those essential components that serve as a basis for evaluating policy in the housing sector.

CONCLUSION

Following the commitment to serve the goals of sustainable development, public welfare is an endeavour to serve all aspects of society and ensure a minimum level of tolerable living conditions for all. In the same line, eliminating housing deprivation through the implementation of a variety of public housing policies and initiatives is an essential step toward achieving this objective. In addition to resolving the housing shortage, the implementation of housing policy has helped the nation's economy expand by fostering the creation of new jobs and more evenly distributing available resources. The way in which a problem is approached is what determines its validity. Some programmes that only allow a small number of beneficiaries to participate have fallen farther behind in the competition for success, which is backed by opportunities to exploit loopholes. However, as a result of the lessons that have been gained and the growing significance of the design of implementation techniques and an organised approach, policymakers have moved away from piecemeal treatments and toward comprehensive solutions for the issue of housing poverty. In the end, this made flexibility possible, which bolsters the adaptability in the local context of implementation, closing the same loopholes in the areas of prospects for economic growth, increased transparency, increased accountability, and a more positive sense of pleasure.

Any policy framework must comply with the scope, constraints, and capacities of the implementing entities in order to be valid. This is because the end result is what is

ultimately most important. If the implementation fails to adhere to the targets and requirements of the schemes, then those schemes' policies remain on paper and appear disconnected from the final result. Therefore, the essential areas that were identified during the implementation of the housing programme become a criterion for evaluating the efficacy of policy in housing and a tool for evaluating its effectiveness after it has been implemented. In addition, these criteria may serve as important learning points that can be taken into consideration when developing new housing policies or initiatives. Because of this, it will be possible to carry out housing policy more efficiently and to satisfy the scheme or objectives of housing policy as nearly as is practically possible. The criteria that have been outlined are sufficient enough to either result in the successful execution of a policy or in its failure to do so. The method in which these vital aspects are governed by the many policy stakeholders will determine how this turns out. The stakeholders will determine the extent to which they are able to manage these essential aspects of policy implementation as well as the manner in which they do so.

A comprehensive understanding of the problem that is being addressed must serve as the basis for the formulation of policy. In addition to that, it needs to include an exhaustive analysis of all of the potential weaknesses. To ensure the success of a housing strategy, it is essential to have a robust structure for the procedure of implementation, to maintain transparency with the beneficiaries, and to encourage their participation.

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